

KEY INDICATORS

With 9,556 hectares, Luxembourg had 7.2% of its farmland under organic management, which was below the EU average of 11.1%. Organic farmland more than quadrupled, similarly to the European Union. In Luxembourg, organic retail sales amounted to 180.3 million euros or 9% of all retail sales, considerably higher than the EU organic share.

ORGANIC FARMLAND

2001

2024

Area* (Share of Total Farmland)

2,003 ha (1.6%)

9,556 ha (7.2%)

Area Growth from 2001 to 2024

377%

ORGANIC LAND USE & AQUACULTURE

2001

2024

Arable Land* (Share of Total)

828 ha (2.4%)

3,869 ha (6.2%)

Permanent Crops* (Share of Total)

25 ha (0.7%)

195 ha (12.4%)

Grassland* (Share of Total)

1,175 ha (1.8%)

5,492 ha (8%)

Aquaculture Production (Share of Total)

N/D

N/D

ORGANIC OPERATORS

2001

2024

Producers (Share of Total)

48 (1.7%)

165 (8.8%)

Aquaculture Producers

N/D

N/D

Processors

28

87

Importers

N/D

6

ORGANIC RETAIL SALES

2001

2024

Retail Sales (Share of Total)

N/D

180.3 M€ (9%)

Per Capita Consumption

N/D

264,3 €

Retail Sales Growth from 2001 to 2024

N/D

Imports

N/D

13 †

Source: FiBL survey based on national data sources, Eurostat and TRACES/European Commission in the framework of the OrganicTargets4EU project

*In conversion and fully organic

KEY INDICATORS

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC FARMLAND IN LUXEMBOURG

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on ASTA, Eurostat and Nic Lampkin

DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIC RETAIL SALES IN LUXEMBOURG

Source: FiBL-AMI Survey based on Biogros

CAP ORGANIC POLICY SUPPORT

The Luxembourg CAP Strategic Plan provides for a more than five-fold increase in the share of agricultural area under organic farming and expenditure on organic support by 2027 compared with 2018, with a funded target of 24% organic by 2027. Support payments per ha for fruit and vegetables are doubled compared with the previous period, with smaller increases for grapes, arable and grassland. Support for conversion is also increased to levels up to 75% higher than maintenance support, reaching 2500€/ha for permanent crops.

CONVERSION & MAINTENANCE

	2018	2027
Land Area Supported (Change from 2018)*	5 kha	24 kha (+394%)
Share of Total Agricultural Area Supported*	3.8%	19.8% (+421%)
Share of Certified Organic Area Supported (Change)*	85%	N/D
Expenditure per Year*	1 M€	8 M€ (+556%)
Expenditure per Hectare Supported*	258 €	342 € (+33%)

SHARE OF CAP RESOURCES

CAP EXP. 2023-2027 ORGANIC SHARE*

Organic Farming Support (P2)*	35 M€	100%
Eco-Schemes (P1)	41 M€	20.7%
Agri-Environment, Climate, Welfare (P2)	129 M€	
Total CAP Expenditure	465 M€	7.6%

*including in-conversion and fully organic land

CAP ORGANIC CONVERSION AND MAINTENANCE PAYMENTS FOR DIFFERENT LAND USES

INDICATOR	YEAR	FUND	GRASSLAND	ARABLE CROPS	HORTICULTURE	FRUIT CROPS	GRAPES
Conversion Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	270	300	850	1200	1350
	2023	P2	400	450	2000*	2500	2500
Change from 2019 to 2023			+48%	+50%	+135%	+108%	+85%
Maintenance Support (€/ha)	2019	P2	220	250	600	800	950
	2023	P2	300	300	1150*	1500	1500
Change from 2019 to 2023			+36%	+20%	+92%	+88%	+58%
Conversion Support Higher than Maintenance	2019		+23%	+20%	+42%	+50%	+42%
	2023		+33%	+50%	+74%	+67%	+67%

P1 (Pillar 1) European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF); P2 (Pillar 2) European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and national co-financing

*Potatoes 700 €/ha conversion, 550 €/ha maintenance

NATIONAL ORGANIC ACTION PLAN

Luxembourg published its fifth national organic action plan at the end of 2025,, with the first one started in 2009. Despite the ambitious growth targets and the high levels of support available (see above), many actions in the previous plan were mainly focused on early-stage scoping of information initiatives. The targets and actions of the new plan are less ambitious than the previous one, although some actions to improve action plan governance are proposed: strengthen role of ComEx, establish reporting system with indicators, involve stakeholders through consultations

TARGETS

	PERIOD	LAND AREA TARGET	OTHER TARGETS
Previous Action Plan	2019-25	20% of UAA by 2025	20% public procurement by 2025
Current Action Plan	2026-30	Increase by 1 percentage point per year to 15% by 2030	30% share of public procurement by 2030

KEY ACTIONS

PREVIOUS ACTION PLAN (2019 - 2025)

Increased payments, simpler eligibility; study of options for conversion support; easier access to investment aid for small and new farms

Market development initiatives for different sectors; supply chain co-operation; networks for new entrants; strong focus in public procurement; regional, national and EU export promotion; support for certification costs

Increased visibility and better communications to relevant audiences at all levels; improve demonstration farms, conversion advice; explore options for specialist advice; compulsory organic modules in agriculture courses; professional training for producers, advisers, processors and traders; research dissemination and priority setting concepts; stocktake of organic statistics and market studies

PRODUCTION

Analysis and optimisation of support payments; support for organic farms for certification costs.

MARKETS

Creation of value chains; development and value-adding for new products or sub-products; development of statistical data on markets for organic products; public procurement through Restopolis/Supply4Future

INFORMATION

Promotion of organic farming with communication plan, network of demonstration farms; integration of processing and trade actors in new projects; organic advisory network meetings; training for producers, advisers and other actors in value chains; experimental fields and variety trials; specific support for research on organic farming, product processing.

CURRENT ACTION PLAN (2026 - 2030)

AQUACULTURE

The organic share of total aquaculture production in Luxembourg is negligible. Luxembourg was not included in our analysis of the EMFF (2014-2020) and EMFAF (2021-2027) operational programmes and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plan for Aquaculture. Organic aquaculture was not highlighted in the current or previous national organic action plans. As the funding is project specific and there is no ring-fenced organic budget, statistics on organic aquaculture support expenditure are not available.

OrganicTargets4EU
www.organictargets.eu

Project Coordinator
Ambra De Simone
IFOAM Organics Europe
www.organicseurope.bio

Authors
Helga Willer
(FiBL, Switzerland)
Nicolas Lampkin
(Thünen-Institut, Germany)
Sabine Reinecke
(FiBL, Switzerland)

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IFOAM
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